

CalWave - xWave Higher Order Dynamics and Autonomous Control Testing

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

CalWave seeks to conduct scaled, experimental prototype testing for a total duration of 10 working days at the W2 Basin at University of Maine. Scaled wave tank testing of a representative scaled wave energy converter prototype in a controlled environment will greatly de-risk CalWave's upcoming deployment of a larger scale prototype off San Diego, California and ensure operation of CalWave's open water demonstrator is safe and efficient.

This experimental testing would be conducted at a point of CalWave's open water demonstration project at which there is little uncertainty in the system specifications of the ocean-going wave energy device that are directly reflected in the scaled experimental testing (e.g. physical properties of the device, properties of the targeted ocean deployment site that can be replicated in the scaled wave tank experiment, final control algorithms).

Hence, the experimental test setup will be more closely aligned to the upcoming large-scale ocean deployment, compared to tank tests performed in previous project stages. This significantly increases the quality of the experimental test results due to lower uncertainty in the correct scaled setup and significantly reduces risk for the ocean deployment.

All proposed wave tank testing conducted under this project will follow guidelines from IEC 62600-103 - Best practices for testing of pre-prototype scale devices.

Post Access: CalWave successfully completed the wave tank testing campaign at UMaine during February 1st, 2021 – February 12th 2021. In this period, CalWave completed 148 distinct cases, totaling 19.1 hours of recorded data.

All testing objectives (See section 3) have been met:

- 1. System identification of the revised absorber geometry revealed changes to the hydrodynamic characteristics of the absorber body. As absorber body design changes were mostly due to hardware constraints for the larger ocean going device, the hydrodynamic similarity with the previous absorber design was desired and confirmed.**
- 2. A set of nine irregular wave cases representative for a scaled open water demonstration in southern California were thoroughly assessed. All nine wave cases showed expected performance results with respect to power absorption. Furthermore, force and stroke estimates were confirmed to be in range of expected values and ensured safe operation of the open water demonstration device at that resource. The data collected will act as a comparison set to data collected via the open water demonstration that will be conducted later this year (2021).**
- 3. An autonomous controller for the xWave device was experimentally assessed using "Combo" wave cases: Concatenated wave cases with different sea state characteristics (H_s , T_p , peak enhancement factor γ). Controller logic on gain scheduling based on autonomous sea state detection was confirmed. Tests revealed a high sensitivity to tuning gains for the wave state estimator with respect to significant wave height. The control logic of autonomous control of the WEC and governing equations facilitating the controls were validated.**

4. **Higher order dynamic models predicted parametric resonance effects of the device that were experimentally assessed: Coupled degrees of freedom and energy spilling in between them was on purpose excited, with the objective to detect the parametric resonance. For specific monochromatic cases, parameter/gain selections, and ramp up times, the parametric resonances were, in fact, detected and observed (which itself is already remarkable). Magnitude of the resonances were, however, significantly lower than analytically predicted; this stems from a lack of viscous drag characterization in coupled degrees of freedom. Furthermore, during irregular waves, parametric resonance barely has the chance to grow and hence, was barely observed.**

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE PROJECT

CalWave is developing a wave energy converter (WEC), called *xWave*, that operates fully submerged and is classified as a submerged pressure differential type. As ocean waves pass over the submerged wave buoy, a pressure differential is created, exciting the absorber in multiple degrees of freedom to oscillate in resonance with the ocean waves. Energy is efficiently extracted using multiple independently controllable power take-off (PTO) units. Based on CalWave's 2-body WEC technology tested in the US DOE's Wave Energy Prize, multiple improvements on absorber geometry and PTO controls have been achieved.

Absorber dynamics are optimized to extract (and not only oscillate) from multiple degrees of freedom. Next to high performance, CalWave found a unique approach to locally adjust to wave excitation loads which allows to effectively shut the device down in storm conditions using a variable geometry on the main absorber.

2 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

2.1 APPLICANT RESPONSIBILITIES AND TASKS PERFORMED

The applicant (CalWave) will provide/bring the following test equipment to the W2 basin:

- WEC prototype
- Tank test PTO and cables
- All Laptops, Controller and DAQ systems including all communication cables required to operate the WEC and the PTO.

CalWave will be responsible for the following tasks:

- Preparation of the WEC prototype and PTO and support in installation of the WEC in the basin as well as installation of PTO on the basin walls
- Control and communication setup
- Wave case run preparation and execution
- All post processing and reporting

2.2 NETWORK FACILITY RESPONSIBILITIES AND TASKS PERFORMED

UMaine will be providing the following test equipment:

- Wave basin with water level set to 5m
- 4-5 wave probes arranged at specified locations at the basin
- Concrete anchors as specified locations providing a connection for mooring tethers
- Support beam or, ideally, bridge running over the basin to run communication cables
- Mounting brackets that connect to the tank walls and provide a mounting interface for the wave tank PTOs. The mounting brackets were successfully used in past wave tank tests
- Qualisys underwater camera system, reflector balls to be mounted to the WEC prototype

- Data acquisition system for wave probe recording

UMaine will be responsible for the following tasks:

- Installation/lifting of the WEC prototype into the basin
- Installation of concrete anchors in the basin
- Setup of wave maker to run different wave cases; Initialization; start/stop
- Calibration of underwater Qualisys system
- Recording of Qualisys data as well as wave probe data

3 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Two weeks of wave tank testing will continue to improve numerical models used continuously throughout the open water deployment targeted for Spring/Summer 2020. Kinematic and dynamic values of the PTO will be measured using a) load cells, b) displacement sensors, c) Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs), d) 3D motion tracking system provided by the facility, and e) pressure sensors for hydrodynamic loads.

The W^2 testing facility at UMaine can create all irregular sea states needed to confirm the xWave's energy absorption performance and high ACE score. Ultimately, results from this tank test can directly be compared to data that will be collected during the open water demonstration starting in Fall 2021. Having a matching, scaled setup of the wave energy converter with minimal uncertainty of device and wave properties allows to do so and achieve the following objectives:

- 1. Objective:** Derive insights into latest absorber geometry iteration hydrodynamic characteristics as well as device dynamics -> System Identification of hydrodynamics and WEC absorber dynamics using forced device oscillation
- 2. Objective:** Performance assessment of the device in a variety of sea states relevant for US West Coast climates -> Acquisition of a comprehensive data set to compare against the equivalent large scale/open ocean operation.
- 3. Objective:** Device controller autonomy and algorithm validation: Autonomous device controller decision in changing sea states. Confirmation of device operations to further increase device design and controller/logic design. Nondimensionalized absorber displacements for specific sea states in which numerically parametric resonance was identified will be compared against theory to assess the actual occurrence of such higher order resonance in experiments.
- 4. Objective:** Assessment if the device can experience parametric instabilities in certain sea states from higher order dynamics -> Check device behavior for specific wave cases with specific controller tunings.

The testing campaign will provide final key results on questions regarding:

1. Changes of absorber geometry in terms of efficiency, survivability (via Objective 1), and de-risking of upcoming open water deployments (via Objective 4).
2. Validate performance in irregular sea states (via Objective 2)

3. Validation of controller autonomous decision-making capabilities to increase confidence for in field utilization (Objective 3)

4 TEST FACILITY, EQUIPMENT, SOFTWARE, AND TECHNICAL EXPERTISE

The Alford W² Ocean Engineering Lab is a 1:50-scale offshore model testing facility equipped with a high-performance rotatable wind machine over a multidirectional wave basin. The lab accurately simulates towing tests, variable water depths, and scaled wind and wave conditions that represent some of the worst storms possible anywhere on Earth.

WAVE BASIN AND WAVE MAKER

The basin is 30 meters long by 9 m wide (98 x 30 ft) and has a working depth of floor of 0 meters to 4.5 meters. The basin contains a 16-paddle wave generator, a beach, a moving wind wall, and an adjustable floor. The 16-paddle wave maker can simulate regular waves and all standard spectra as well as custom random seas with directional waves and a range of frequencies. It can produce wave angles greater than +/- 60 degrees relative to the basin center line. Waves can be maximum height of 0.6 m at T = 1.65 seconds, and 0.8 m at T = 2.3 seconds.

Figure 1: Pictures of the W² Basin at the University of Maine Advanced Structures & Composites Center.

GENERAL & PERSONNEL

- CalWave's prototype model will be shipped to the W² wave basin.
- The W² basin will be accessed during January 2021 for a total of 10 working days.
- All instruments / wave gages are pre-installed prior to testing.
- Mooring pulleys and mooring weights are already in place from testing in August.
- Model shipping and packing from the facility is the responsibility of CalWave
- At least one knowledgeable personnel from UMaine are requested to operate the wave maker at the tank, as well as setup of the Qualisys system.

BASIN & BASIC FACILITY REQUIREMENTS:

- The water depth in the basin is requested to be (from SWL to bottom of tank): **4.5m**.
- For mooring, weights will be placed at certain locations of the floor, rigidly fixing a pulley system (provided by CalWave – part of the setup) in place.
- UMaine will provide a support beam or bridge above the model to run cables.
- Mounting possibilities on the side walls to place a winch type PTO on. (Connection frame or similar mounting would be provided by CalWave).
- Characterization of reflection coefficients for the basin (if available) would be provided by UMaine
- Regular 110V power outlets around the tank are requested.
- CalWave requests at least five calibrated wave sensors/gages at distinct locations (scheme to be provided) with sampling frequencies $f > 50$ Hz.
- For optimal validation purposes of higher order device dynamics, CalWave would require underwater motion tracking (as the device operates submerged). The W2 tank at Maine provides these sensors which had been used in two previous tank tests at Maine. The tank PTO units need to be mounted to the side walls of the wave tank.

5 TEST OR ANALYSIS ARTICLE DESCRIPTION

The prototype is a scaled version of CalWaves submerged WEC technology with a square top view shape and slanted corners. The absorber hull has pressure sensors integrated for measuring the pressure field. An Inertia Measurement Unit (IMU) is mounted on board of the device recording device velocity and acceleration for advanced controls.

Next to high performance, CalWave found a unique approach to locally adjust to wave excitation loads to effectively shut the device down in storm conditions using a variable geometry on the main absorber. Testing variable geometry WEC devices in past wave tank campaigns has been limited and hence CalWave's proposed testing advances the state of the art in the field.

Four PTO units are used and connected to the device via tethers. The PTO units are of winch type and located outside the wave tank (typically rigidly mounted on the tank walls). Tethers connect the PTO winches to the absorber hull and control the displacement and forces on it. Submersible load cells are used to measure PTO forces and PTO motor encoder measures displacement.

A Froude scaled prototype was manufactured. Dimensions and specifications of the demonstration scale device were used to derive correlating prototype specifications and dimensions. Demonstration scale device parameters were obtained from device optimization in a parametric time domain simulation framework. The absorber body was manufactured out of sheet metal with the outer hull consisting of the following pieces: The CAD assembly of the hull can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CAD assembly of 1:25 scale absorber body hull

Table 1: Manufactured sheet metal hull pieces.

Hull Pieces	Pieces	Weight per piece (kg)	Total weight of type (kg)
Outside Corner	4	1.55	6.2
Outside Side	4	3.3	13.2
Inside Corner	4	0.85	3.4

Inside Side	4	1.87	7.48
Top / Bottom Plate	2	2.69	5.38

Figure 3 shows pictures of the manufactured absorber body. On the left side the absorber body is entirely assembled including the hatch. The right side shows the partially assembled absorber body and the internal foam structure to reach the design excess buoyancy of the device.

Figure 3: Manufactured scaled absorber body for experimental testing at the W² wave tank at the University of Maine.

Figure 4: Absorber body installed at the W2 basin. Here, the absorber is floating on the water surface, ready for the next tests.

Due to weight and size restrictions in the scaled prototype body, it was decided to remove the PTO hardware from the device and place it on the wave tank side/bridge.

The prototype PTO units are designed to obtain the largest degree of flexibility in setting PTO parameter, as well as to be able to execute any kind of desired force tracking for device control. To achieve this, an all-electric prototype PTO scheme was chosen. The electric PTO can effectively be used to emulate any kind of PTO behavior. Any kind of PTO behavior based on the feedback measurements, PTO/Tether force, PTO velocity and displacement, can be implemented

One PTO unit consists of a 4-pole, NEMA-34 frame BLDC electric motor connected to a winch shaft around which the PTO tether wraps in a single layer. A planetary gearbox is mounted in between the winch shaft and the motor shaft effectively changing the speed to force ratio in a favorable direction. The motor shaft is coupled to the planetary gearbox, so that the low-speed side of the gearbox shares the same speed and torque as the winch shaft.

The taut mooring/PTO tether connected to the bottom of the absorber body is guided through a pulley sitting on the basin floor back to the PTO location. It then wraps (in a single layer) around the PTO drum. Motor, Gearbox, and PTO shaft, as well as fairlead to guide the PTO tether towards the drum are rigidly connected in a frame.

An example PTO unit as it was installed at the W^2 basin is shown in the following Figure 5:

Figure 5: Tank test PTO for precise force control mounted to the side of the W^2 wave tank.

For system identification tests it was desired to feed the PTO units with an open loop noise signal which was achieved by cutting open the closed loop at the sensor fusion and device control algorithm block and feeding a force set point signal representing the desired open device loop (and still closed PTO tracking loop) noise excitation.

The closed device control loop as well as the PID controller inside the motor drives were tuned on the PTO bench before the experimental testing campaign.

The achieved force set point tracking capabilities achieved with the controller is near perfect. For a random irregular excitation (displacement) of the PTO the force set point and actual tracking signal is compared in the following Figure 6:

Figure 6: Example time resolved force set point and loadcell measurement / tracking signal showing a particularly good set point tracking capability of the controller & PTO units. Here, the PTO unit was randomly excited with an irregular signal with a common period and magnitude.

Force tracking capabilities are obviously frequency dependent and were assessed for the full range of expected PTO frequencies using broadband excitation. Figure 7 shows an example of the PTO tracking capabilities in the frequency domain:

Figure 7: Frequency dependent force tracking capabilities.

6 WORK PLAN

6.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP, DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM, AND INSTRUMENTATION

Wave maker calibration took place before experimental testing. Next to irregular wave cases defined by the US DOE Wave Energy Prize, nine additional wave states of a southern California wave resource were scaled down to a tank scale:

Scripps Wave Cases (SWS) and - 1:25 Scale - UPDATED & TRUNCATED												
Label	Dir [Deg]	Tp [s]	Te [s]	Hs [m]	Gamma	Spread	Repeat Time [s]	Repeats N	Phase	Total Duration [s]	Total Duration [min]	Waves per Repeat
SWS 1	0	3.13	2.69	0.1	1	Inf.	782.6	3	Identical repeats	2347.87	39.15	250
SWS 2	0	4.02	3.46	0.1	1	Inf.	1006.2	3	Identical repeats	3018.69	152.95	250
SWS 3	0	4.90	4.21	0.1	1	Inf.	1225.0	3	Identical repeats	3675.00	73.00	250
SWS 4	-45	4.90	4.21	0.15	1	Inf.	1225.0	3	Identical repeats	3675.00	84.00	250
SWS 5	-15	3.13	2.69	0.16667	1	Inf.	782.6	3	Identical repeats	2347.87	39.25	250
SWS 6	0	3.58	3.07	0.23333	1	Inf.	894.4	3	Identical repeats	2683.28	44.75	250
SWS 7	0	2.24	1.92	0.11667	1	Inf.	559.0	3	Identical repeats	1677.05	28.00	250
SWS 8	0	4.47	3.84	0.2	1	Inf.	1118.0	3	Identical repeats	3354.10	56.00	250
SWS 9	0	5	4.29	0.25	1	Inf.	1250.0	3	Identical repeats	3750.00	67.10	250

All wave cases were designed according to IEC standards including sufficient repeats as well as wave per repeat.

For gain scheduling tests combination sea states were designed that switched wave cases to emulate changing seas on a ~7-minute basis:

Irregular Wave States Combination (Combo) - 1:25 Scale for Maine Tank - Gain Scheduling												
Label	Dir [Deg]	Tp [s]	Te [s]	Hs [m]	Gamma	Spread	Repeat Time [s]	Repeats N	Phase	Total Duration [s]	Total Duration [min]	Waves per Repeat
Combo 1	-	-	-	-	1	Inf.	-	Total of 5	Different Sea states concatenated together	1500	25.00	
#1 PIWS1	0Deg	1.46	1.25	0.09	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	274.4
#2 PIWS4	0Deg	2.54	2.18	0.08	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	157.5
#3 PIWS2	0Deg	1.97	1.69	0.11	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	203.3
#4 PIWS5	0Deg	3.05	2.64	0.23	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	131.1
#5 PIWS1	0Deg	1.46	1.25	0.09	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	274.4
Combo 2	-	-	-	-	1	Inf.	-	Total of 5	Different Sea states concatenated together	1500	25.00	
SWS 7	0	2.24	1.92	0.11667	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	178.9
SWS 2	0	4.02	3.46	0.1	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	99.4
SWS 6	0	3.58	3.07	0.23333	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	111.8
SWS 3	0	4.90	4.21	0.1	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	81.6
SWS 1	0	3.13	2.69	0.1	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	127.8

Note that the waves per repeat as well as the single repeat per wave state are not according to IEC standards. By design these wave cases were not meant to produce performance estimates or statistic of other PTO/device parameter but to assess the device capability to change PTO and device controller/parameter gains for different incident seas.

The total experimental setup includes multiple sensors to measure PTO kinematic and kinetic signals, device displacement and velocity, as well as absorber hull pressure and incident wave elevation. A list of all sensors used in the setup can be found in the following Table 2:

Table 2: Instrumentation list including measurement quantity, used sensor, and data sampling rate in Hz.

#	Measurement	Sensor	Unit	Sample Rate [Hz]	Data Logging Rate [Hz]
1	Wave Elevation	Capacitive Wave Probe	mm	50	50
2	Wave Elevation	Capacitive Wave Probe	mm	50	50
3	Wave Elevation	Capacitive Wave Probe	mm	50	50
4	Wave Elevation	Capacitive Wave Probe	mm	50	50
5	Wave Elevation	Capacitive Wave Probe	mm	50	50
6	Wave Elevation	Capacitive Wave Probe	mm	50	50
7	Absorber x	QualiSys Motion Tracking	cm	100	100
8	Absorber y	QualiSys Motion Tracking	cm	100	100
9	Absorber z	QualiSys Motion Tracking	cm	100	100
10	Absorber Rx	QualiSys Motion Tracking	cm	100	100
11	Absorber Ry	QualiSys Motion Tracking	cm	100	100
12	Absorber Rz	QualiSys Motion Tracking	cm	100	100
13	PTO 1 Tension	Loadcell FUTEK QSH01269	N	25000	100
14	PTO 2 Tension	Loadcell FUTEK QSH01269	N	25000	100
15	PTO 3 Tension	Loadcell FUTEK QSH01269	N	25000	100
16	PTO 4 Tension	Loadcell FUTEK QSH01269	N	25000	100
17	PTO 1 Encoder Pos	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm	25000	100
18	PTO 2 Encoder Pos	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm	25000	100
19	PTO 3 Encoder Pos	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm	25000	100
20	PTO 4 Encoder Pos	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm	25000	100
21	PTO 1 Encoder Vel	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm/s	25000	100
22	PTO 2 Encoder Vel	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm/s	25000	100
23	PTO 3 Encoder Vel	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm/s	25000	100
23	PTO 4 Encoder Vel	Motor Encoder- Electrocraft RP34	cm/s	25000	100
24	Hull Pressure Upstream Heave	Pressure Sensor – AMETEK SDT	Pa	25000	100
25	Hull Pressure Upstream Heave	Pressure Sensor – AMETEK SDT	Pa	25000	100
26	Hull Pressure Upstream Surge	Pressure Sensor – AMETEK SDT	Pa	25000	100
27	Hull Pressure Downstream Surge	Pressure Sensor – AMETEK SDT	Pa	25000	100
28	Absorber Body IMU	xSens IMU - 200	m, m/s	60	60

PTO Forces

To obtain PTO force measurements FUTEK loadcells with a maximum force rating of 1335 N are used. The following Table 3 summarizes the loadcells calibration values for the FUTEK loadcells used to measure each PTO/Mooring tether force:

Table 3: Loadcell calibration table.

Loadcell Calibration		
FUTEK Loadcells		
Max		
Rated:	300 lb	1335 N

Loadcell #	Item#	S/N	Model	Output Value (mV/V)	Offset (V)	Connected PTO
1	QSH01269	604728	LSB302	1.668388	0	1
2	QSH01269	604729	LSB302	1.671081	0	2
3	QSH01269	734686	LSB302	1.670893	0	3
4	QSH01269	734687	LSB302	1.670702	0	4

Absorber Position/Velocity/Acceleration

To obtain position, velocity and acceleration of the submerged absorber body for at least 3 DOF (Heave, Surge, Pitch) and preferable in all 6 DOFS (Surge, Heave, Sway, Roll, Pitch, Yaw) a submerged motion tracking / underwater Qualisys setup was used. If required, the real-time motion tracking data is available as supplemental signals as a control input. The Qualisys motion tracking sample rate is set to 100 Hz.

For data acquisition and control of most of the sensors/hardware a NI cRIO unit is used. This allows for very precise control and data sampling with rates up to 25 kHz (using the cRIO's FPGA processor). The following Table 4 provides a preliminary summary of DAQ channel for both measuring signals from hardware/sensors as well as control of the PTO units.

Table 4: DAQ cRIO channel list including PTO affiliation, the specific signal measured, the processor used for control/DAQ as well as the sample rate.

Module	Channel	PTO	Hardware	Signal/Command	Processor	Sample Rate
9361 Digital Counter	CTR0	PTO1	Motor Encoder	PTO1 Displacement	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR1	PTO2	Motor Encoder	PTO2 Displacement	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR2	PTO3	Motor Encoder	PTO3 Displacement	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR3	PTO4	Motor Encoder	PTO4 Displacement	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR4	PTO1	Motor Encoder	PTO1 Velocity	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR5	PTO2	Motor Encoder	PTO2 Velocity	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR6	PTO3	Motor Encoder	PTO3 Velocity	FPGA	25 kHz
	CTR7	PTO4	Motor Encoder	PTO4 Velocity	FPGA	25 kHz
9237 Analog Bridge	Bridge 0	PTO1	FUTEK Loadcell	PTO1 Tether Force	FPGA	25 kHz
	Bridge 1	PTO2	FUTEK Loadcell	PTO2 Tether Force	FPGA	25 kHz
	Bridge 2	PTO3	FUTEK Loadcell	PTO3 Tether Force	FPGA	25 kHz
	Bridge 3	PTO4	FUTEK Loadcell	PTO4 Tether Force	FPGA	25 kHz
9401A DIO	Driver 1	PTO1	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Enabling Motor Driver	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	Driver 2	PTO2	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Enabling Motor Driver	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	Driver 3	PTO3	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Enabling Motor Driver	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	Driver 4	PTO4	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Enabling Motor Driver	Real Time OS	1 kHz

9263 AO	AO0	PTO1	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Motor Current Control	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AO1	PTO2	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Motor Current Control	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AO2	PTO3	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Motor Current Control	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AO3	PTO4	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Motor Current Control	Real Time OS	1 kHz
9205 AI						
	AI0	PTO1	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Read Motor Current	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI1	PTO2	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Read Motor Current	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI2	PTO3	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Read Motor Current	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI3	PTO4	CPP Universal Servo Driver	Read Motor Current	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI4	Absorber	Pressure Sensor	Hull Pressure	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI5	Absorber	Pressure Sensor	Hull Pressure	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI6	Absorber	Pressure Sensor	Hull Pressure	Real Time OS	1 kHz
	AI7	Absorber	Pressure Sensor	Hull Pressure	Real Time OS	1 kHz

6.2 TEST AND ANALYSIS MATRIX AND SCHEDULE

TEAMER - Wave Tank Testing						
Subject / Category	Task / Priority	Duration (Working Days)	Intended Experiments	Wave Set	Methodology	Analysis of Results
0. Device Setup						
1. Baseline Setup Functionality Testing & Rapid Device Characterization	Task 1	2 days (2 cumulative)	Unpacking, Tank Installation of WEC, Device & Instrumentation Staging, Motion System Calibration			
		2 day (4 cumulative)	<p>A: Basic working principle validation to ensure all sensors, Tank test PTO units, and communication is working.</p> <p>B: Device excitation with pink noise wave signals for rapid characterization.</p>	No Waves / Monochromatic Waves / Pink Noise Waves	<p>A: Baseline device setup is run with monochromatic waves for baseline working principle & setup verification. Some short sets of single monochromatic waves are sufficient.</p> <p>B: Pink Noise wave excitation is used to verify initial device characteristics.</p>	<p>A: Basic working principle is qualitatively assessed; PTO control capabilities (e.g. F tracking) and PTO tuning parameters are quantitatively assessed.</p> <p>B: Device intrinsic impedance for different configurations is obtained from these experiments. This acts as direct input into the advanced controls applications.</p> <p>General: Qualisys and wave gages all write correctly, Trigger signal works and is synched with wave start signal.</p>
2. Advanced and Automated Controls Testing	Task 2	2 days (6 cumulative)	<p>A: Device performance and behavior assessment in Irregular Wave Cases for PTO control methodologies for power absorption.</p> <p>B: Device behavior assessment in large irregular wave cases for device control methodologies targeting survivability.</p> <p>C: Automated Controller tuning testing in changing irregular waves.</p>	<p>A: Irregular Waves</p> <p>B: Large Irregular Waves</p> <p>C: Changing irregular waves (timeseries provided)</p>	<p>Setup of device and controller parameter. Set device and PTO load limit parameter.</p> <p>Run irregular waves sets for convergence on performance & loads.</p> <p>Tuning of Controller a) inbetween runs and b) autonomously by controller.</p>	<p>A: Comparison of performance, PTO loads, reactive power requirements etc. for actively controlled performance assessments.</p> <p>B: Assessment of force to watch cycle/ displacement tradeoff for survivability cases.</p> <p>--> Assessment of autonomous controller testing.</p>
			<p>Testing of exact operating sequences / PTO control algorithms as integrated into open water demo controller: Assess typical operating procedures:</p> <p>a. Submergence of device</p> <p>b. Maintenance/floating position stabilization</p> <p>c. Change from different performance control strategies</p> <p>d. "Device self assessment" & Auto-SID</p>	Irregular Waves (See tab "Wave Cases")	<p>Full PTO impedance Model including all sub-components are used to model the PTO forces acting on the prototype in the basin.</p> <p>Wave cases & operating procedures are initialized.</p> <p>Exact control signal sequence / structure / code is used to execute the specific operating procedure targeted.</p> <p>Device behavior is recorded and assessed.</p>	<p>This testing allows to check and debug actual control sequence code intended to be used in the open water demonstration.</p> <p>Testing in a controlled laboratory environment ensures that procedures and signals send are correct, derisking the actual deployment.</p>
3. Break-down						
		1 day (10 cumulative)	Removal of WEC Prototype, Removal of Connecting Hardware, Packing up and clean up; Final Data Transfer & Debriefing			

For Task1 of the above table, respectively objective 1 of the work proposal the following irregular wave runs were conducted:

CalWave X25 - Sorted Subset - Maine - Feb 2021												
Objective	Run ID	Waves					Control Mode	Gain CTRL			Min Tension Gain [N/N]	Force Set-point Gain [N/peak]
		Name	Spectrum	Dir (°)	Tp	Hs		k1	k2	k3		
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 1	#4	SWS1	BS	0	3.13	0.1	Adv. No Auto	0.285714286	0.166666667	500	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 2	#5	SWS1	BS	0	3.13	0.10	Adv. No Auto	0.285714286	0.166959742	500.9	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 3	#6	SWS2	BS	0	4.02	0.10	Adv. No Auto	0.310068571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 4	#7	SWS2	BS	0	4.02	0.10	Adv. No Auto	0.310068571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 5	#9	SWS3	BS	0	4.90	0.10	Adv. No Auto	0.257497143	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 6	#10	SWS5	BS	-15	3.13	0.17	Adv. No Auto	0.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 7	#11	SWS4	BS	-45	4.90	0.15	Adv. No Auto	0.257497143	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 8	#12	SWS4	BS	-45	4.90	0.15	Adv. No Auto	0.257497143	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 9	#13	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Adv. No Auto	0.457142857	0.339882333	1019.6	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 10	#14	SWS8	BS	0	4.47	0.20	Adv. No Auto	0.24	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 11	#15	SWS6	BS	0	3.58	0.23	Adv. No Auto	0.365714286	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 12	#16	SWS9	BS	0	5.00	0.25	Adv. No Auto	0.137142857	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irr Wave Assessment - Objective 13	#17	SWS9	BS	0	5.00	0.25	Adv. No Auto	0.137142857	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28

As well as the following rapid device assessment cases to satisfy Objective 1 of the work plan:

MIMO SID Runs												
SID - Device Setting A - PTO F Setting A	#52	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting A - PTO F Setting A	#53	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting A - PTO F Setting A	#54	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting B - PTO F Setting A	#55	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting B - PTO F Setting A	#56	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting B - PTO F Setting A	#57	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting A	#58	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting A	#59	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting A	#60	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting B	#97	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting B	#98	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting B	#99	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28
SID - Device Setting C - PTO F Setting B	#100	MIMO_	Pink	0	N/A	N/A	Noise	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.114286	0.28

Autotuning runs for Task 2 of the run table, respectively Objective 3 of the work plan are listed in the following table:

Sea State Estimation and AutoTuning												
Sea State Estimation - Config A	#105	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A	#106	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A - 150% Gai	#107	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.175	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A	#108	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A	#87	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config B	#88	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config B - 150% Gai	#89	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.175	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Mono Sweep for Correction factor of estia	#109	Mono	Mono	0	4s - 2s	0.06	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#110	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#111	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#112	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#113	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#114	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Comparison no autotuner	#115	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Standard	0.31	0.17	500.00	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#116	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#121	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Comparison no autotuner	#122	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Standard	0.31	0.17	500.00	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#123	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Comparison no autotuner	#124	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Standard	0.31	0.17	500.00	0.11	0.28
Combo 2 - Autotuning interp test	#125	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Combo 1 - Comparison no autotuner	#126	Combo	BS	0	Var	Var	Standard	0.31	0.17	500.00	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A	#90	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A - 150% Gai	#91	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.18	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config B	#93	SWS7	BS	0	2.24	0.12	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A	#94	SWS2	BS	0	4.02	0.10	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config A - 150% Gai	#95	SWS2	BS	0	4.02	0.15	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28
Sea State Estimation - Config B	#96	SWS2	BS	0	4.02	0.10	Assymmetric Inter	Var	Var	Var	0.11	0.28

Finally, parametric resonance cases under Objective 4 of the work plan are listed below:

Parametric Resonance Assessment												
Assessing Resonance in 1st Mathieu branch												
Search for Resonance in 1st branch	#20	Mono	Mono	0	2.22222	0.12	Assymmetric KC	0.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Search for Resonance in 1st branch	#21	Mono	Mono	0	1.818182	0.12	Assymmetric KC	1.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Search for Resonance in 1st branch	#22	Mono	Mono	0	1.538462	0.12	Assymmetric KC	2.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Search for Resonance in 1st branch	#23	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	3.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Search for Resonance in 1st branch	#24	Mono	Mono	0	1.176471	0.12	Assymmetric KC	4.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Search for Resonance in 1st branch	#25	Mono	Mono	0	1.052632	0.12	Assymmetric KC	5.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Assessing Yaw Instability 1st branch with different PTO gains												
Parameter Search - Set1	#26	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	7.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parameter Search - Set1 + 150% wave gain	#27	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.18	Assymmetric KC	8.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parameter Search - Baseline + 150% wave	#28	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.18	Assymmetric KC	9.314285714	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parameter Search - slightly smaller frequ	#29	Mono	Mono	0	1.428571	0.12	Assymmetric KC	10.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parameter Search - higher PTO k	#30	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	11.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parameter Search -largest instability - rep	#31	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	12.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance - 1st Mathieu branch rerun												
Case 26 as reference case	#76	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	14.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 26 with higher kp	#77	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	15.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 26 with no kp	#78	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	16.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 26 with altered absorber position	#79	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	17.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Assessing Resonance 1st branch with different PTO gains again												
Resonance - reconfirm findings	#42	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	19.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance	#43	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	20.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance	#44	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	21.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance	#45	Mono	Mono	0	1.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	22.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance during irregular waves												
Irregular 1st Branch	#46	Inst1	gamma = 5	0	1.333333	0.1	Assymmetric KC	24.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irregular 1st Branch - 150% gain of Inst1	#47	Inst1	gamma = 5	0	1.333333	0.15	Assymmetric KC	25.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irregular 1st Branch - 150% gain of Inst1	#48	Inst1	gamma = 5	0	1.333333	0.15	Assymmetric KC	26.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 47 as ref case in Mathieu Branch 1	#84	Inst1	gamma = 5	0	1.333333	0.15	Assymmetric KC	27.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 47 with altered absorber pos	#85	Inst1	gamma = 5	0	1.333333	0.15	Assymmetric KC	28.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Searching for Resonance 2nd Mathieu branch												
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#32	Mono	Mono	0	2.857143	0.12	Assymmetric KC	30.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#33	Mono	Mono	0	3.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	31.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#34	Mono	Mono	0	4	0.12	Assymmetric KC	32.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#35	Mono	Mono	0	4	0.12	Assymmetric KC	33.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#36	Mono	Mono	0	3.333333	0.12	Assymmetric KC	34.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#37	Mono	Mono	0	2.857143	0.12	Assymmetric KC	35.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#38	Mono	Mono	0	2.5	0.12	Assymmetric KC	36.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Assessing Yaw Instability 2nd branch with different PTO gains												
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#39	Mono	Mono	0	2.5	0.12	Assymmetric KC	38.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#40	Mono	Mono	0	2.5	0.12	Assymmetric KC	39.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Parametric Resonance 2nd Mathieu branc	#41	Mono	Mono	0	2.5	0.12	Assymmetric KC	40.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Irregular Waves - Resonance 2nd branch												
Case 50 as Reference: Parameter 2nd Brar	#80	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.15	Assymmetric KC	42.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 50 with higher kp	#81	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.15	Assymmetric KC	43.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 50 with altered absorber position	#82	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.15	Assymmetric KC	44.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Case 50 with altered absorber position	#83	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.15	Assymmetric KC	45.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance 2nd Branch - 100% gain of Inst	#49	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.1	Assymmetric KC	46.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance 2nd Branch - 150% gain of Inst	#50	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.15	Assymmetric KC	47.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28
Resonance 2nd Branch - 150% gain of Inst	#51	Inst2	gamma = 5	0	2.666667	0.15	Assymmetric KC	48.31428571	0.166667563	500.0	0.114286	0.28

6.3 SAFETY

All relevant safety protocols of UMaine will be acknowledged and followed. Safety hard hats as well as safety glasses need to constantly be worn at the wave basin. COVID related safety protocols of UMaine with respect to quarantine and/or COVID testing will be acknowledged and followed.

Post-Access update: All safety regulations were followed and worked out well. CalWave would like to highlight the great safety concept and plan that UMaine had in place to handle COVID as well as work related risks appropriately.

6.4 CONTINGENCY PLANS

If the facility is unexpectedly not available during the proposed time frame or if COVID related restrictions do not allow travel/testing at UMaine, experimental testing is postponed.

Post access note: Due to COVID related delays anticipated testing had to be rescheduled from December 2020 and was ultimately conducted during the first two weeks of February 2021.

6.5 DATA MANAGEMENT, PROCESSING, AND ANALYSIS

6.5.1 Data Management

Data quality assurance will be provided on site with first order post processing after each test. Data collection will start before waves are started and continue for at least 1 minute once wave generation stops. This ensures that data captures initial setup condition (e.g., mooring pretension from hydrostatic buoyancy) and transient ramp-up/down effects.

“Raw” data from all sensors are logged including Sensor ID, timestamp, units, and measured values and saved in the LabView “TDMS” format. Sensors measured with other DAQ systems than the NI hardware are saved in an appropriate file format (e.g., text or CSV files). All data will be stored on local machines and backed up on online storage.

Motion Tracking Data (3 rotational, 3 translational DOFs) are stored in MATHWORKS MATLAB .mat files. Wave Elevation is stored in .txt files with one column for each of the introduced wave gages.

CalWave will submit the following results to the MHK-DR according to CalWaves TEAMER application:

1. Non-dimensionalized device displacements in irregular sea states; txt or .mat files:
The file “CalWave_TEAMER_DispData_Norm.mat” includes normalized device motion data for the set of irregular wave states. Each data structure includes a time vector as well as motion data for all six degrees of freedom. The following data structure is used:

Time Vector	Surge [m/m]	Sway [m/m]	Heave [m/m]	Roll [Rad/Rad]	Pitch [Rad/Rad]	Yaw [Rad/Rad]
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2. Performance improvements comparisons to Wave Energy Prize results; The following comparison shows experimentally validated performance improvements compared to WEP results:

Performance improvement relative to WEP

Case	CalWave Maine (1:25 Scale) Performance improvement relative to WEP results	Comments
IWS1	183.50%	AEP Yield relevant
IWS2	192.38%	AEP Yield relevant
IWS3	96.29%	AEP Yield less relevant
IWS4	147.68%	AEP Yield relevant
IWS5	115.34%	AEP Yield less relevant
IWS6	163.88%	AEP Yield less relevant

3. Controller behavior (e.g. gain scheduler) for changing sea states; excel tables with gain maps normalized to maximum values for interpolation in the gain scheduler are added to the submission of this report. The maps were used during automated gain tuning by the controller to derive best estimations for gains for different parts of the device controller starting from PTO control gains to device submergence and position setpoints.

The provided excel table includes also the reference vectors with sea state information on H, and frequency omega respectively, allowing the derivation of the maps.

6.5.2 Data Processing

Raw data will be post processed using s Matlab and/or Python. Data acquired during each run is downloaded from the data acquisition system directly after finishing the test case. Important signals such as force and kinematic signals are plotted to inspect for any missing data or obvious inconsistencies. Front panel parameter for each case are recorded via automated screenshots at the start of every experimental case.

Wave power calculation accounts for the intermediate water depth and no deep-water approximation simplification is used. This results in a different contribution of wave power to the total incident wave state power as each frequency in the wave spectrum is evaluated using the dispersion relation. The schematic on the right-hand side shows the general steps taken to derive the average incident wave power from the wave gage data.

Multiple repeats of the same phase realization are run (typically three) allowing to conduct WEC power calculation in the time domain and for the second repeat, which reduces uncertainties from transient effects.

Wave cases are typically repeated twice (leading to a total of 6 repeats with two different phase realizations), increasing the signal to noise ratio and reducing measurement uncertainty.

6.5.3 Data Analysis

First and last repeat of the phase realization of an irregular wave case will be discarded from the experimental data set. Solely the middle repeat will be used as it will not include any transient wave propagation/reflection effects. Data will be normalized with relevant parameter (e.g., resonance periods, peak forces, peak displacements, velocities, peak instantaneous power values) to allow for calculation of advanced metrics ratios.

Motion data collected were transformed from a Qualisys native file format to MATLAB data structures. Any offsets during calm water/when the device was sitting completely at rest in the basin, were subtracted from subsequent traces. No filtering or smoothing was applied to collected PTO force and displacement data as data acquisition already performs a down sampling procedure from FPGA at 25kHz to the real time OS with 1 kHz. Data acquisition was performed at 100 Hz, which is sufficient for post processing. No further down sampling took place for post processing. All data was collected according to IEC standards.

7 PROJECT OUTCOMES

7.1 RESULTS

7.1.1 OBJECTIVE 1 – SID / DEVICE CHARACTERISTICS

Device characteristic is derived using MATLAB System Identification routines. Further reference on how to derive device impedances using MIMO system identification can be found in Sandia National Lab reports on advanced controls¹. Plots are generated using the derived intrinsic impedance matrices and the MATLAB “bode()” plot command. Xlabel ticks are adjusted to represent important range.

The following plot show the device characteristics via the device admittance Y for three main DOFs, Surge, Heave, and Pitch with raw data, as well as the result of the transfer function via system identification:

The resulting MIMO model was compared with additional data sets with exceptionally good results proving that an excellent model for control design was derived as shown in Figure 8:

Figure 8: Comparison of derived models / device characteristics with additional experiments.

¹ <https://energy.sandia.gov/programs/renewable-energy/water-power/projects/advanced-wec-dynamics-and-controls/>

7.1.2 OBJECTIVE 2 – REFERENCE CASES FOR US WEST COAST CLIMATES

In the following the normalized device displacement for two of the reference cases is plotted for each of the 6 DOFs. The plots are directly created from the data submitted in the CalWave_TEAMER_DispData_Norm.mat file by plotting the displacement over the time vector:

Reference case 2 (orange) vs. reference case 1 (blue):

Furthermore, PTO parameter such as forces, velocities and stroke were assessed. An example plot of time resolved, normalized quantities is found below:

Figure 9: Example of time trace of normalized PTO characteristics.

Note, that Force, Velocity, as well as PTO Stroke is shown for all four PTO units.

Statistics derived from the recorded data are provided in the following figure (normalized). These will act as reference values to compare to data collected from the upcoming open water demonstration.

Maine February 2021 - SWS Cases										
SWS #	Run ID	Absorber Pos Set [norm]	Absorber Pos Measured [norm]	Av. Power Upstream [norm]	Av. Power Downstream [norm]	Max PTO Vel [norm]	Max PTO Stroke [norm]	Max PTO Force [norm]	Net Device av. Power [norm]	Wave Power [norm]
SWS1	Run05	0.38	0.37	0.42	0.44	0.55	0.24	0.77	0.43	0.10
SWS2	Run07	0.42	0.41	0.29	0.35	0.51	0.97	0.70	0.31	0.13
SWS3	Run09	0.33	0.34	0.19	0.28	0.43	0.21	0.65	0.22	0.16
SWS4	Run12	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.68	0.59	1.00	0.79	0.50	0.71
SWS5	Run10	0.40	0.42	0.82	0.92	1.00	0.31	0.93	0.85	0.42
SWS6	Run15	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.62
SWS7	Run13	0.40	0.41	0.93	0.62	0.87	0.11	0.85	0.57	0.10
SWS8	Run14	0.83	0.84	0.93	0.78	0.70	0.29	0.78	0.62	0.57
SWS9	Run17	1.00	1.00	0.70	0.72	0.50	0.25	0.66	0.51	1.00

Each of the quantities was obtained by using max, min, mean commands over the multiple repeats of the collected data. All values in each column are normalized via the largest value for each statistical value.

Max normalized PTO forces for all cases show, that the force capabilities of the PTO are well utilized in all sea states leading to high utilization of the PTO CAPEX. While PTO stroke shows a larger deviation, the PTO stroke for a rotary PTO is of way less significance compared to the PTO – in other words, large strokes do not pose a problem or increased cost to the PTO design.

Average power absorption capacity factor for the upstream and the downstream PTO units is calculated as 63%, respectively 64% showing a high utilization rate among different sea states which is beneficial for power electronics design.

7.1.3 OBJECTIVE 3 – AUTONOMOUS CONTROL VALIDATION

Figure 10 shows an example time trace of the autonomous controller behavior for a set of cascaded sea states. Based on identification algorithms for sea state detection using hull pressure data information and IMU appropriate gains are chosen for optimal performance.

Note, that the autonomous controller can identify sea states and adjust control gains on different time scales e.g. taken a larger share of data into account for long term statistical sea state adjustment, or shorter data snippets to adjust for wave groupiness or faster fluctuating sea states. The adjustment of the time window taken into account for the auto controller is an optimization variable.

Figure 10: Autonomously controlled wave time trace

The concatenated sea states for the above auto controller are as following:

Irregular Wave States Combination (Combo) - 1:25 Scale for Maine Tank - Gain Scheduling												
Label	Dir [Deg]	Tp [s]	Te [s]	Hs [m]	Gamma	Spread	Repeat Time [s]	Repeats N	Phase	Total Duration [s]	Total Duration [min]	Waves per Repeat
Combo 1	-	-	-	-	1	Inf.	-	Total of 5	Different Sea states concatenated together	1500	25.00	
#1 PIWS1	0Deg	1.46	1.25	0.09	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	274.4
#2 PIWS4	0Deg	2.54	2.18	0.08	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	157.5
#3 PIWS2	0Deg	1.97	1.69	0.11	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	203.3
#4 PIWS5	0Deg	3.05	2.64	0.23	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	131.1
#5 PIWS1	0Deg	1.46	1.25	0.09	1	Inf.	400	1		400	6.67	274.4

Note that only a single repeat of each irregular wave state was used in the concatenation rather than full sets of three repeats as focus of this assessment is the auto controller behavior during changing sea and to a lesser degree to optimality of scheduled gains.

Excel tables with gain maps normalized to maximum values for setpoint derivation in the gain scheduler are added to the submission of this report. The maps were used during automated gain tuning by the controller to derive best estimations for gains for different parts of the device controller starting from PTO control gains to device submergence and position setpoints.

7.1.4 OBJECTIVE 4 – PARAMETRIC INSTABILITY / HIGHER ORDER DYNAMICS

Parametric instability between the Yaw and Heave DOF was assessed. Energy transfer between these modes is not identifiable via common linear order dynamic and requires second or higher order modeling and evaluation of Mathieu diagrams. For one example case (see run table, Case 42) the time resolved absorber motion as well as the FFT of translatory degrees of freedom and rotational degrees of freedom are shown in Figure 10.

As it can be seen from this example case, the yaw-heave parametric resonance takes about 150 seconds after start of the monochromatic waves to pick up, grows over a timeframe of 50 seconds and then converges to an upper oscillatory amplitude bound without further growth.

As the FFT shows, the Yaw instability show a period doubling behavior typical for the instability branch assessed which appears exactly at half the excitation frequency.

Figure 11: Time resolved absorber motion and FFT showing the yaw parametric resonance picking up and ultimately reaching a bounded oscillatory amplitude.

To achieve this parametric resonance behavior the PTO controller gains as well as the exact monochromatic wave excitation period had to be very carefully tuned to hit the instability branch. To assess if parametric heave yaw resonance can occur during open ocean deployments irregular wave cases were assessed. Using the exact device and PTO parameter identified during monochromatic waves in which the resonance picked up, irregular waves were used for device excitation.

To really push the initialization of the parametric resonance, specific wave spectra with an extremely high peak enhancement factor at the wave excitation frequency leading to monochromatic resonance build up were utilized. The peak enhancement factors were in the order of magnitude of 6, exceeding parameter typically matching ocean wave spectra.

Figure 11 shows again the time resolved absorber motion as well as the FFT of translatory degrees of freedom and rotational degrees of freedom.

Figure 12: Time resolved absorber motion and FFT showing little parametric yaw resonance.

As it can be seen from the time resolved rotational absorber displacements, the yaw resonance barely picks up. Even when larger yaw displacements occur, the motion quickly dies out by the irregular motion and excitation of the device.

The above analysis was conducted for all device and wave configurations found to show parametric instability characteristics. For all irregular wave cases the yaw parametric resonance never exceeded acceptable values.

It is quite remarkable that careful higher order modeling correctly predicted the existence of such a heave-yaw mode resonance couple and energy exchange. However, concerns about the parametric instability severely impacting device behavior, performance, or safety in a real ocean deployment was not found.

7.2 LESSON LEARNED AND TEST PLAN DEVIATION

All objectives laid out in CalWave's initial proposed test plan were successfully executing. Preparation of wave cases for the wave maker calibration was carefully conducted before testing occurred which greatly sped up the testing.

Time a wave tank facility is valuable and limited, and such experimental campaigns require flexibility in test execution. Slight deviations from experimental setup need to be accepted due to time constraints. Similarly, wave tank testing requires flexibility in the exact order and execution of planned runs and not every run that ultimately is conducted as a valuable experimental test can be listed and identified before the actual testing.

1. A daily comparison run with a simple monochromatic wave should be conducted each morning and compared to previous days to ensure test equipment and the setup did not change and all equipment works properly.
2. IMU-based position estimates using sensor fusion approaches can, for correct setup and filtering, yield exceptionally good WEC motion data. Potentially the use of Qualisys setups can be removed in future wave tank tests, further reducing setup effort and costs.
3. Irregular wave cases should be designed with multiple repeat periods with the same phase realization for each individual wave case run, significantly increasing signal to noise ratio for FFTs and data analysis.
4. Data recording on CalWave's end was synchronized with wave probe recordings using an external trigger which extremely valuable (and mandatory) for successful wave excitation System Identification.
5. COVID related delays as well as additional project expenses due to the pandemic (e.g. additional travel time due to quarantining requirements at the location of testing) should be handled flexibly by the TEAMER program. This was handled very well for our project and CalWave would like to thank the TEAMER team for this flexibility.

8 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Project objectives were achieved with a rigorous data set allowing for thorough assessment of device performance, controller logic validation, as well as studying occurrence and effects of parametric resonance effects.

Objective 1 – Device Characteristics

- As expected, the slight device absorber design change did not lead to fundamentally different hydrodynamic characteristics compared to previous absorber designs. The change was solely due to engineering related changes and hence, the little to no change in device characteristics was desired.

- Rapid MIMO system characterization via noise excitation was once again validated as a suitable tool for a quick evaluation of design changes and is recommended as a standard procedure for any wave tank testing.

Objective 2 – Reference Irregular Wave Cases

- The acquisition of a reference set for an open water deployment as well as the confirmation of device performance is highly recommended shortly before any open water deployment.
- Device performance and operational characteristics were in range and findings further increased confidence in successful operation of the open water device to be deployed.

Objective 3 – Autonomous Control

- Autotuning of device and PTO parameter was confirmed. While choosing correct gains mostly requires good characterization of device and PTO impedance, as well as sufficiently large gain matrices for set point decision making, autonomous sea state detection is challenging.
- Careful combination of device on board sensor information such as pressure sensors and PTO information in combination with device impedance can, however, provide a robust and accurate estimate of sea states.
- Computational parameters such as maximum frequencies to consider as well as length of (sea state) windows to assess are important to tune.
- Performance increases from correct autotuning compared to slow varying device parameter/gains justifies autonomous controller development.

Objective 4 – Parametric Resonance / Higher Order Dynamics

- It was possible to excite the parametric resonance using monochromatic waves that was predicted by higher order dynamic models of the device. Slight differences were found in the wave excitation required to excite the resonance.
- Device and PTO gains must be in a very narrow range to excite the undesired parametric resonance.
- In irregular waves (even with extremely high peak enhancement factor $\gamma = 5$ at the parametric resonance frequency), the resonance barely picked up and was continuously disturbed by other waves or device effects such as minimum or maximum line tensions enforced by the controller.
- Parametric resonance effects can differ with the scale of the device due to mismatch in how viscous forces scale. This must be kept in mind when scaling up towards large devices. Careful observance of any pre-cursors of parametric instability in large scale/open water deployments must be kept in mind.

Future testing should focus on assessing additional, nonsymmetric tether configurations for performance increase as well as further assessment of advanced controllers acting in the absorber body frame. Autonomous control features should, from now on, become the standard for wave tank testing for the xWave concept.

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CalWave is looking forward to further the work and build upon findings documented in this report in the future TEAMER projects.

